

ON THE USE OF LINGUISTIC CORPUS IN LANGUAGE EDUCATION

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Abstract. The article deals with language corpuses, the history of their creation, requirements for the creation of corpuses, the possibilities of using corpuses in teaching languages, and the issues of creating a corpus of Uzbek language.

Keywords: text corpus, corpus linguistics, authentic material, computerized language learning, linguistic variability.

Резюме. В статье речь идет о языковых корпусах, об истории их создания, требованиях к созданию корпусов, возможностях использования корпусов в обучении языкам, о вопросах создания корпуса узбекского языка.

Ключевые слова: корпус текстов, корпусная лингвистика, аутентичный материал, компьютеризованное языковое обучение, лингвистическая вариативность.

Rezume. Maqolada til korpuslari, ularning yaratilish tarixi, korpus yaratishga qo'yiladigan talablar, korpuslardan til ta'limida foydalanish imkoniyatlari, o'zbek tili korpusini yaratish masalalari haqida fikr yuritilgan.

Tayanch so'zlar: matn korpusi, korpus lingvistikasi, autentik material, kompyuterlashtirilgan til ta'limi, lingvistik variativlik.

Currently, the number of representatives of different countries and nationalities who want to learn the Uzbek language is increasing day by day. In this regard, the need arises to look for new effective methods of teaching Uzbek as a foreign language. Naturally, in this process, the comparative typology of languages, as well as other methods and tools, are of particular importance.

In the modern educational process, it has become relevant not to give knowledge on language levels by teaching a second language, but to talk about the formation and development of communicative competence in students. It is known that communicative competence is the ability to carry out speech activity in accordance with the goals and state of communication in a particular field of activity from the language under study [6]. It is based on a set of skills that allow you to participate in oral communication. The formation of communicative competence is a multifaceted, multi-step process. In solving these and similar issues, teachers are helped by modern digital technologies. At the moment, the

effective use of a large-scale didactic tool, the so-called "linguistic corpus", in the study and teaching of languages, pays off.

Corpus linguistics is a branch of linguistics that deals with the development, creation and use of text corpora [2]. This term was introduced into science in the 1960s in connection with the beginning of the process of creating Corps. And since the 1980s, the improvement of computational techniques has led to the further development of Corpus Linguistics [Q.: 4].

Corpus linguistics appeared in the 60s of the 20th century mainly on the basis of English material, but soon Corps of other languages began to emerge as well. In 1963, he attended Brown University in the United States. Francis and G.As the first text corpus was created by scholars such as Kuchera [Q.: 1], this corpus consisted of 500 texts. Each of these texts contained two thousand words, which were English texts written in the 15 types of prose genre that were considered the most popular in the United States. Also attached to this housing is a frequency indicator, as well as some statistics.

Corpus refers to an electronic complex of texts in one or more languages, compiled on the basis of certain parameters. The corpus is a collection of texts in written and oral forms, differentiated by the fact that it is numbered from a collection of simple texts, that is, it consists of a set of texts that are analyzed electronically, placed in special metka/symbols and stored on a computer, as well as linguistic annotations that regulate data and that information [3; 79].

From foreign experiments, it can be seen that when the electronic corpus of the language appeared, the possibilities of demonstrating the variety of the language and researching linguistic material grew significantly, expanded.

If the search standards are correctly specified in the process of working with the corpus by a researcher or language teacher or language learner, the above various signs directly facilitate, speed up the process of performing a number of tasks, such as collecting factual material, analyzing it, preparing material for the lesson to be conducted, checking the practical application of the studied language units.

In general, each definition given to the Corpus recognizes the following:

1) many texts must be issued electronically (on the internet or on disk); 2) in order to carry out linguistic analysis, special signs should be worn (metka) on the language material; 3) it is necessary to include "live speech" materials in the composition of the corpus, the material should be real, not edited, the variability of language units should be indicated; 4) as a result of the analysis performed, it should be possible to distribute the collected language material on the basis of

various principles (for example, genre, date of creation of the text, by topic, etc.) [5; 28].

In the process of teaching Uzbek as a foreign language, the teacher often faces a number of problems associated with a lack of textual materials that meet all modern requirements. This is especially manifested in working with an English-speaking audience. Differences in the origin and morphological characteristics of English and Uzbek languages raise many questions in learners, both in terms of semantics and in terms of the logical structure of the sentence, the entire text. Therefore, it will take a long time to prepare a new material that will help to increase the interest of students in learning the Uzbek language, which will clearly show them the application of language units in practice. Since the national corpus of the Uzbek language is not created, in such cases it is possible to solve the problem by using other language corpora (such as English or Russian) for the purpose of translating and comparing texts. The creation of the Uzbek version of the language Corps, its enrichment and development remains one of the urgent tasks of both theoretical and practical linguistics.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. Брауновский корпус, свободный доступ с сайта университета Лидс: <http://corpus.leeds.ac.uk/protected/>
2. <https://ru.m.wikipedia.org/wiki>
3. Козлова Н. В. Лингвистические корпуса: определение основных понятий и типология. Вестник НГУ. Серия: Лингвистика и межкультурная коммуникация. 2013. Т.11 Выпуск 1. – С. 79.
4. Плунгян В. Что такое корпус языка? <https://postnauka.ru/video/7783>
5. Sinclair J. Corpus, Concordance, Collocation. Oxford, 1991. –Р. 171.
6. Центр современных методик преподавания. <http://www.dioo.ru/harakteristiki.html>

